

THE ANALYSIS OF NEOLOGISMS IN MASS MEDIA**Umirova Dilshoda Husniddin qizi**

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ABSTRACT: There's no doubt that globalization and presentation of neologisms have extended in later a long time as innovation has created more quickly than ever individuals communicate and, in some cases, make modern words or expressions which can effectively spread all over the world and gotten to be well known much appreciated to the web and mass media. The contemporary investigation aimed to discover the linguistic evaluation of neologism associated with Coronavirus (COVID-19). Recently, a brand-new coronavirus disorder COVID-19 has emerged as a breathing contamination with widespread difficulty for worldwide public fitness hazards. However, with every passing day, an increasing number of showed instances are being stated global which has alarmed the worldwide government consisting of the World Health Organization (WHO). In this examine, the researcher makes use of the time period neologism this means that the coinage of latest phrases. Neologism performed a widespread function in the course of the records of epidemic and pandemic. The consciousness of this examine is at the phenomenon of neologism to discover the introduction of latest phrases in the course of the outbreak of COVID-19.

Key words: Antibody, aerosol, antigen test, quarantine, flashback, babalicious, Merkozy, affixation, morphemes, archaism, pia colada

АННОТАЦИЯ: нет никаких сомнений в том, что глобализация и представление неологизмов расширились в последнее время, поскольку инновации создавались быстрее, чем когда-либо. Люди общаются и в некоторых случаях произносят современные новые слова или выражения, которые могут эффективно распространяться по всему миру и стать широко известными в сети и в средствах массовой информации. Современное исследование было направлено на обнаружение лингвистической оценки неологизма, связанного с коронавирусом (COVID-19). Недавно появилось новое корона вирусное

заболевание COVID-19, представляющее собой респираторную инфекцию, которая широко распространена во всем мире. Однако с каждым днем в мире фиксируется все большее количество выявленных случаев, что встревожило мировое правительство, состоящее из Всемирной организации здравоохранения (ВОЗ). В этом исследовании исследователь использует неологизм периода времени, то есть введение новейших фраз. Неологизм выполнял широко распространенную функцию в ходе записи эпидемий и пандемий. Цель исследователя находится в феномене неологизма, чтобы обнаружить введение новейших фраз в ходе вспышки COVID-19.

Ключевые слова: Антитело, аэрозоль, антигенный тест, карантин, флешбэк, бабалициус, Меркозы, аффиксация, морфемы, архаизм, пина колада

The Latin word 'corona' means 'crown'. The virus is called 'corona' due to its crown-like form and spikes. In the wake of the COVID-19 outbreak, to outline new conditions new phrases had been coined and they may be extensively used on print and social media. In January and February 2020, there are key phrases related to COVID-19 while, others associated with worldwide events, f.e. Donald Trump's impeachment, Australian bushfires, locust swarms in East Africa, the assassination of Qasem Soleimani, and inquiries into the Astros sign-stealing scandal, etc. "In January 2020, the phrases specifically relate to naming and describing the virus: coronavirus, SARS, virus, human-to-human, respiratory, flu-like," explored the OED in an analysis. "By March, the key phrases mirror the social effect of the virus, and problems surrounding the scientific response: social distancing, self-isolation and self-quarantine, lockdown, non-important (as in non-important travel), and put off are all mainly frequent, as are PPE and ventilator." ¹

The outbreak of Covid – 19 has resulted in lots of phrases getting used along less not unusual place phrases which unfold as rapid as the virus. Some current phrases have commenced to be used and feature grow to be not unusual place in lots of elements of the world. Here are a few examples in English, Uzbek an Russian.

¹ <https://www.neologism.com/>

Corona virus	Koronavirus	Каронавирус
Quarantine	Karantin	Карантин
Case fatality	O'lim xolati/ko'rsatkichi	Показатели смертности
Epidemic	Epidemiya	Эпидемия
Pandemic	Pandemiya	Пандемия
Epicenter	Epitsentr	Эпицентр
Face covering	Maska taqish	Покрывать лицо
Face mask	Maska	Маски для лица
Infected	Kasallangan	Зараженные
Lockdown	Lokdaun (karantin)	Локдаун (карантин)
Personal protective equipment	Shaxsiy ximoya vositasi	Средства индивидуальной защиты
Social distance	Ijtimoiy masofa	Социальная дистанция
Self-isolation	O'zini yakkalash	Сама изоляция
Vaccine	Vaksina	Вакцина
Remote education	Masofaviy ta'lim	Удаленька, дистанционка

TABLE 1

Although these words are neologisms in Uzbekistan and other part of the world, nowadays vaccine, remote education, self-isolation changed into common words through Covid-19. Many people utilized these words a daily expression not only in mass media, but also in social networks used these phrases and expressions.

So as to acquire the required information, I started by searching for studies that worked with similar ideas of neologism in times of Covid-19 as mine; still as these typically specialized in alternative aspects of this analysis field, I alone was able to use them to urge an outline over the assorted freshly designed neologisms. it's an undeniable fact that main resource for this study is that the Coronavirus Corpus, that contains over 892 million words from quite twenty countries. Clearly, the collected data predominately consists of a various vary of newspaper articles that are being collected since Gregorian calendar month 2020, so as of having the ability to check the frequency of "Coronavirus, Rona, Covid-19 and Sars-CoV-2". I merely sought for the amount of appearances of the selected words. For the second a part of analysis I started watching numerous collocations occurring directly before or behind one among the terms. To slim it right down to a possible amount, I chose round the 5 most frequent collocations for every word and it was thus able to compare their use in context. If we tend to come back to information analysis and results. A neologism is defined, in step with Bußmann (1990: 520), as a freshly fashioned expression that's recognized by a minimum of a locality of a language community, if not even recognized in general, to label new ideas in numerous elements of life. Consequently, the terms "Coronavirus, Rona, Covid-19 and Sars-Cov-2" will be denoted as new neologisms that emerged throughout the pandemic though these terms refer all to an equivalent novel disease, they are adopted in distinctive frequency within the following the correct results of my analysis will be displayed. [2]

This unit contained with different examples for using neologisms in mass media, magazines and journals. This investigation devoted to explain the coinage of words in daily usage related to corona virus and its etymology, definition and the creation of this neologism. Given all conclusions and fact are used according to the early European scientists' investigation, moreover

² <https://www.facebook.com/business/ads>, last accessed on 17/7/2020

this process connected with my academic year, therefore during this article some phrases and expressions remembered the COVID-19 and helped to write the whole section without stopping.

COVID as a neologism.

When we listen to the news, we sometimes hear new words that we have never heard before but are quickly assimilating into our everyday vocabulary. You probably notice presenters rubbing elbows and donning face masks as you watch updates on the pandemic situation in your nation. In order to maintain social distance, people avoid exchanging handshakes and stand apart from one another.

Here are a few new terms and phrases that have been included into our language. Utilize this glossary to induce commonplace with terms frequently utilized in scope of the novel coronavirus, which causes COVID-19. They are unused neologisms which is the family of coinage words of crown infection:

Aerosol: A little particle or bead that's suspended within the air.

Antibody: A protein your immune system makes in reaction to a disease. In the event that you've got antibodies for the coronavirus in your blood, it implies you have got been contaminated with this virus at a few point (indeed in case you never had any symptoms).

Antibody test: Also called a serology test, this checks to see on the off chance that you have got antibodies in your blood that appear that you just were already contaminated with the virus.

Antigen test: A sort of diagnostic test that checks to see in case you're right now contaminated. The test looks for proteins (antigens) in a test taken from your nose or throat. Antigen tests are quicker than PCR tests, but they are less exact and have the next chance of wrong positives (meaning that they're more likely to say you've got the contaminate).

Quarantine: The observe of staying home and aloof from others for a minimum of five days when you've been exposed to COVID-19 to ascertain if you get symptoms and to avoid spreading the virus if you're carrying it. When you quarantine, get tested at least 5 days after your last contact, albeit you don't have symptoms, and take safety measures till ten days after you were last exposed to COVID: anticipate symptoms, wear a well-fitting mask (NIOSH-approved N95 respirators provide the foremost protection), avoid travel, and keep one's eyes off from those who

are at high risk of catching or obtaining sick from COVID. Isolate at once and acquire tested if you develop symptoms. R_0 : Pronounced r-naught, this can be the "basic fruitful range" of a contagious disease: the typical number of further cases that directly result from one-person conveyance it into a community. COVID-19 is believed to possess associate degree R_0 of 2.2-2.7, which suggests that the primary one who has it in an exceedingly community can probably infect 2 or three others, and {people} new infected people will every maintain to infect another two to a few people, chop-chop spreading the virus. [3]

Redelivery (Veklury): A medication made to treat Ebola (but ne'er approved for that purpose), redeliver is that the initial treatment to be granted full approval by the FDA to treat COVID-19. Evidence shows that those treated with redeliver recovered in concerning eleven days compared to fifteen days for those treated with a placebo.

The usage of neologisms in British newspapers

Neologisms are frequently directly attributed to a particular author, work, time period, or event. Neologism is a term that is used across many disciplines, not just linguistics. With regard to some science in particular, we may observe that they all capture the central idea. Always something new exists. All of the aforementioned definitions can be combined to form a new one. The following could be this definition: a new word, phrase, or expression that is contemporary in origin and is frequently used to apply or synthesize new ideas to clarify current ideas or to modernize outdated vocabulary.

Neologisms are particularly helpful for identifying innovations, novel phenomena, or previously held beliefs that have adapted to a new cultural setting. We shall adhere to these criteria throughout the current study because it appears to have every essential element of a neologism.

The term "neologism" was first used in English in 1803 as has already been established. However, the German, Italian, and French versions of this phrase predated the English translation, so the past 65 years, when the corresponding terminology were created. Neologism in literature

³ <https://www.facebook.com/pg/facebookapp/about/>, last accessed on 17/7/2020

was compared by the time's critics it is believed that the language was constantly being expanded and receiving new lexical units.

Linguistic change as a whole as a decaying process. Therefore, the term "neologism" was solely utilized negatively and was criticized for both linguistic and aesthetic reasons. This neologism's earlier connotation and the mindset it expresses are still relevant today.

But even so, it was clear that the language of literary expression should not be completely confined even in the second half of the 18th century. Neology, which defined the introduction of "authorized" or "proper" new words into language was therefore given an ameliorative doublet to the derogatory neologism.

The traditional definition of neologism is equivalent to archaism, barbarism, Gallicism (in English), and Anglicism (in French). (The American Heritage Dictionary of the English Language, Fourth Edition, 2000) It is related to purism. Word qualities like neologism or archaism are historically contingent. Only by looking at a certain time period of a language's social life can one assess the degree of word topicality and attribute to neologism the characteristics of archaism.

When they were first used, words like cable television (1966), CD-ROM (1988), flashback (1966), environment (1972), hip-hop (1985), or pia colada (1967) were novel; nonetheless, now, most people are familiar with them all. [4]

Regarding neologisms and their age, there are many diverse points of view. Determining when a new word turns into a neologism is the key challenge. According to some academics, a word is a neologism if you think it is one. According to some academics, a word cannot be deemed a neologism if it is older than 25 years.

The classification of the phenomenon under examination is one of the techniques employed by academics in any science. For instance, in linguistics, we study the many elements of speech and are familiar with the roles that words play in sentences. In terms of neologisms, it is important to note that there is no agreed-upon classification system and that the issue has not yet been resolved. Various neologism characteristics have been considered in various categories developed by academics.

⁴ https://www.facebook.com/ChapStick/?tn-str=k*F, last accessed on 17/7/2020

The structural-semantic classification of neologisms is how Russian linguist L.A. Haham organizes neologisms by classifying them according to their structure and semantics.

1. A word whose meaning and form are both novels.
2. The meaning is new but the form is older
3. The form is new but the meaning has already been expressed in another word.

It is possible to think of the structural classification of neologisms as following what eminent Russian linguist E. V. Rosen categorizes neologisms in accordance with their structure, therefore, it can be regarded as neologisms' structural classification.

1. Neologisms are words that can appear alone or as components of other new words.
2. Recently introduced morphemes in the language
3. A word made up of preexisting morphemes combined in a novel way.

The obvious difference between Rosen's and Haham's methods is semantics, a neologism's definition. Rosen simply considers a word's structure while making decisions. However, he takes into account both its structure and meaning.

Identify these types of groups as phonological, semantic, or syntactic borrowings or neologisms. It is also possible to group all neologisms by the subject they relate to, resulting in a science, politics, and other theme categories are numerous.

In every language, neologisms represent innovation. Every day, new words are produced and their quantity is rapidly increasing in English. Neologisms frequently use established word-formation techniques like affixation and compounding. Any combination can have a heading. Primary lexical class, and neologisms contain all possible combinations: skinhead, red-hot, over-quick. Examples of affixation are girlhood and marketing. Additionally, you may create neologisms by combining words (such as Spanish language, and vodkatini) and acronym zing.

Random access memory (RAM) The same is true of acronyms (vet, lab, flu). Neologisms are occasionally created through conversion (to network, to nurse). Radio, newspapers, magazines, and television are examples of mass media. Communications that quickly reach a big number of people. The mainstream media create newspapers and other media have had a significant impact on the English language in this regard. It is important to mention broadcasting because it is their

responsibility to report events as they occur. As a result, they frequently require fresh terminology to express novel events, concepts, and creations.

Consequently, journalists are people who contribute significantly to the creation and dissemination of neologisms. When we look at the history of English newspaper writing, we see that it dates back to the seventeenth century. In the early newspapers, there was only news and no commentary, like commenting was viewed as going against journalism's core values.

In the nineteenth century, newspaper language was identified as a specific type of style, distinguished by a particular communicative objective and a unique linguistic structure (Morrison, 1932). As has already been mentioned, mass media is not merely a source of information. A word must be widely acknowledged in order to "remain alive" public speaking and usage by celebrities, including politicians, novelists, etc. (1995, Barnhart). A coinage should depend on the editor and the type of dictionary it is used with. [5]

One characteristic may have a higher importance than another depending on the editor and the type of dictionary into which a coinage should be entered. A normal dictionary only accepts around 200 of the thousands of new words that are developed each year that meet the aforementioned requirements.

Throughout the inquiry, I have examined neologisms from The Guardian, a well-known British newspaper. The editions from 2001 and 2008 are the ones I've picked. It was done on purpose because I was curious to see whether there were some forms of formation use that were used more frequently than others and what topics they were associated with. I then used various classification methods, including structural, structural-semantic, and classification in accordance with, to categorize the examples of neologisms. [6]

The instances of neologisms were then categorized using a variety of classification techniques, including structural, structural-semantic, classification according to specific parts of speech, and classification according to thematic groups they belong to or have been employed in.

⁵ <https://www.facebook.com/events/226579545120477/>, last accessed on 17/7/2020

⁶ <https://www.facebook.com/groups/lessstuffmorelife/>, last accessed on 17/7/2020

According to Rosen's categorization, the first structural kind of neologisms is the one that is most frequently encountered; it includes neologisms made up of morphemes that can occur both alone and as components of new words, such as apathy-inducing and car-music.

Compounding is a particularly effective method of generating neologisms, as it has been mentioned previously. Thus, it has been demonstrated in practice. I can say that the majority of neologisms fall into the second version of neologisms based on the results of my attempt to classify the obtained data using the structural-semantic categorization of neologisms. Their new shape and preexisting meaning—overused, people-spot—are distinguishing characteristics. People try to express old concepts using novel combinations of already-existing words, which leads to the creation of neologisms and the enlargement of the vocabulary.

Nouns make up the largest group when neologisms are categorized by which part of speech they belong to, including hubsters, campus-visit, and office-fodder. A noun is a word used to refer to a specific person, location, object, quality, or action. In fact, the function of nouns in language is to serve as neologisms for new things, innovations, happenings, and their characteristics. [7]

Numerous neologisms that are members of or have been employed in the group of neologisms connected by the issue of description, in which I included the words that characterize defining qualities of things or people, such as fuzzy-minded, over-stimulated, and half-pretending. It would be obvious from the definition of neologisms that they signify and characterize new things. When describing certain situations, authors of articles often try to invent and employ more expressive sentences. Furthermore, in order to clarify my words, I want to add some examples of neologisms in British newspapers.

⁷ <https://www.facebook.com/groups/lessstuffmorelife/?ref=bookmarks>, last accessed on 17/7/2020

Word	Original meaning	Extended meaning
<i>Galileo</i>	an Italian astronomer	a European navigation system
<i>outing</i>	a trip or excursion	naming people as homosexuals in public
<i>surf</i>	to ride on waves	to use the Internet
<i>Jedi</i>	a character in Star Wars	a member of an official religion
<i>viper</i>	a poisonous snake	a marihuana smoker

TABLE 2

Neologism	Meaning	Source
<i>Merkozy</i>	Sarkozy and Merkel's alliance	Guardian 12/5/11
<i>chocotherapy</i>	therapy by chocolate	Guardian 8/13/05
<i>flirtberrying</i>	to flirt via BlackBerry™ mobile phones	Daily Mail 4/3/12
<i>babelicious</i>	an extremely attractive girl (babe + delicious)	Guardian 7/16/12
<i>piloxing</i>	a fitness program combining Pilates and box	Daily Mail 4/28/12
<i>Yahooligans</i>	hackers attacking Yahoo® search engine	Guardian 3/9/06
<i>scare-saurus</i> ¹³	a frighteningly looking elderly person (dinosaur)	Daily Mail 11/30/12

TABLE 3

In the first table there are given neologisms, original meaning as well as extended meaning. However, these words are utilized not only in newspaper style, but also, they can be used in other any kinds of speaking style. [8]

⁸ <https://englishexplorations.check.uni-hamburg.de/neologisms-formation-processes/>

When it comes to the second table, all words in it utilized in British magazines and newspapers. It is obvious that there are given new words and their definition and also in order to prove my words there is given their source also. [9]

CONCLUSION

It is a fact that during these chapters which we investigated the history of neologisms, word formation and the analysis of neologisms in newspaper style, therefore we can conclude that neologisms are quite essential in daily life because some technological items, another cultures 'phrases are really challenging to explain that neologisms are the best way to pronounce and explain what you are going to say. Neologism is also the way of creating new phrases, slangs, words that contribute to improving language's evaluation.

If we come to the usage of coined words in newspaper style and social media that is a modern way to expand the language's range and it is also time - saving because instead of saying «Control», it is better to use "CTRL". The unit which is called word form gave readers to understand what is blends, acronyms, loan words, abbreviations that can help to make author's ideas in a short and understandable way. [10]

After investigating this topic, I totally understood that neologisms should teach both at school, and at high education in order to aware about the ways of creating words in easy way. Neologisms are also can feel another atmosphere unlike another words and languages with an unusual character. I believe that these chapters and units could give an enough information and the analysis of neologisms in a real lifestyle with the example of COVID-19.

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⁹ <https://www.scientific.net/AMR.255-260.1622>

¹⁰ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S187704281631343X>

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